

Estimating the Heterogeneous Effects of Regulations: a new Bayesian Method.

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Abstract

This study evaluates the performance of regulatory policies in foster environmental and technical efficiency in electricity sector of a panel of European Union countries. The contribution to the current literature is two-fold. First, the regulation analysis is enriched considering, along with market regulation indicators, the effects of the environmental policy stringency. Second, the estimation strategy use Bayesian shrinkage estimator able to deal with bias aggregation problems and cross-country heterogeneity due to the different transmission channels through which regulatory policy is implemented. Results highlight divergent behaviors at country level. The direct impacts of the market and environmental regulatory policies on productivity are negative, but countries differentiate in the degree at which they are able to compensate these negative effects.

Keywords: electricity sector, Malmquist Index, market and environmental regulation, Bayes estimator

JEL: C21, L51, L94, O47, Q58

Declarations of interest: none.

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1. Introduction

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2019), it has become a priority in the electricity sector to provide this crucial service with special concern reserved to energy efficiency as well as the reduction of green house gas emissions (GHGE). The Energy Efficiency Directive 2018/2002 imposed European Union (EU) countries to implement energy efficiency programs to all sectors, with the aim to lower energy demand and energy costs for companies. Therefore, assessing the performance of electricity sector becomes crucial for this strategic sector. Moreover, evaluating the efficiency of power generation needs to encompass the environmental impact of power generation and the standard indexes for productivity need to be revised. Technical and environmental efficiency well fulfills this requirement, as adjusts changes in productivity according to the levels of the produced GHGE.

Given the economic and environmental relevance of electricity sector, market and environmental regulatory policies have a central role in driving efficiency and the economic effects of these two regulations are of central interest to policymakers. Nevertheless, empirical analyses of literature have led to rather weak evidences. Practical problems are related to the limited temporal and cross-section dimension of the data as well the estimation strategies applied. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, literature assessing the impact of regulatory policies on productivity, has not yet included the negative externalities of electricity sector. Finally, the majority of studies looking at the role of regulation in the efficiency of electricity sector have focused on single policy or single instrument without considering the coexisting effects of both

market and environmental regulations.

This paper contributes to the literature in two ways. The first is to evaluate the performance of both market and environmental regulations in a panel of EU countries, in fostering environmental and technical efficiency (ETE), which is computed through the total factor productivity (TFP), a multiple input-output efficiency measure that encompasses, along with the power generation, the GHGE. As policy designs impact ETE through various country-specific channels, such as the fuel mix employed in power generation, the current technology frontier as well as the starting level of productivity, we investigate the cross-country heterogeneity of different regulatory policies. The effects of market and environmental regulatory policies are evaluated using OECD's indexes: the Product Market Regulation (PMR) index and the Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) index, respectively. The second is methodological and proposes a novel technique to model heterogeneous effects of regulatory policies among EU countries, using a Bayesian shrinkage estimator (BSE). Empirical evidences considering the aggregate effects may suffer from aggregation bias problems. Panel data analyses usually model heterogeneity through either a fixed or random effect model (FE and RE model, respectively). In the former, the heterogeneity between cross-section units is specified by individual intercept terms, while in the latter, the heterogeneity is captured by individual error components. However, heterogeneity among countries can arise from the effects of regulatory policies that have differentiated impact on TFP. Nevertheless, previous empirical specifications in the literature have assumed that the coefficients of the explanatory variables, the slope parameters, are the same for all cross-section units, which is unduly restrictive.

Our approach treats the regression coefficients (instead as fixed variables) as random variables with a probability distribution, thus limiting the number of parameters to be estimated. Operationally, the BSE allows the parameters' estimates to be derived as the weighted average of pooled regression and the individual time series regressions. The Bayesian framework allows overcoming poolability assumption of the slopes parameters assuming regressors' coefficients be random variables that may vary among countries, even if they share a common dynamics as they are drawn from the same joint probability distribution.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on the previous empirical results, Section 3 shows the method applied in the empirical analysis, Section 4 presents data and Section 5 provides the main results. Conclusions and policy implications are presented in Section 6. Appendixes A and B provide econometric framework and results of preliminary analyses.

2. Background and Literature Review

Understanding the impact of environmental policies on productivity is crucial for the design and choice of policy packages. Empirical evidence on the link between regulatory policies and TFP at industry level is ambiguous. Early studies tend to find a negative effect, while more recent ones suggest a positive link. These weak conclusions source from measuring only the economic performance, without adjusting TFP for the presence GHGE as bad output that has to be hindered as the power generation grows. The traditional literature, the so called Pollution Haven Hypothesis, has perceived environmental policy as burdensome to the economic performance

since it forces firms to devote part of resource to pollution prevention and abatement that are not usually considered as added value. A number of more recent studies develop a Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) for U.S. electricity plants specifically tailored for production function with bad output (Cherchye et al., 2015; Agee et al., 2014; Färe et al., 2014 and Jaraité and Di Maria, 2012) but they do not encompass assessments of the combined effect of market and environmental policy instruments. Cherchye et al. (2015) use cross-section data of 573 plants and evaluate efficiency setting a multi-output production function that explicitly gives negative sign to the fossil-fuel electricity. Agee et al. (2014) use 10-year (1988-1997) firm panel data and estimate a multiple-input, multiple-output directional quadratic distance function highlighting the need to ponder the production relationships among pollutants when an efficient cap and trade system is designed. Färe et al. (2014) estimate the ETE for a balanced panel of 87 coal fired plants from 1995 to 2005 using instead an output oriented perspective and a weak disposable production set of pollutant and electricity. They calculate the potential increase in good output production in a simulated scenario where the observed levels of GHGE are optimally allocated among plants via a tradable permit system. Consistent with the so called Porter Hypothesis, these papers surmise that environmental regulatory policy incentives the innovation, the efficiency and the within industry reallocation that increase productivity.

Opposite conclusions have been derived by Jaraité and Di Maria (2012). They correlate the pre-reformed EU electricity industry performance with the germinal ETS and compute the efficiency measures adjusted for the presence of pollutant bad output. The derived empirical evidence are consistent with the traditional literature, that is

environmental regulation slow down productivity growth in its two main dimensions: the technological frontier shift and the technical efficiency.

Although these empirical studies encompass an analytical framework to measure production efficiency consistently with the presence of bad output, they do not evaluate the concurrent impacts on ETE of two types of determinants, the market and environmental regulations.

Other studies focused on the effectiveness of market or environmental regulations in foster the sustainability of electricity sector, but the scopes are narrowed to measure their effects on GHGE levels and carbon intensities (see among others Farzin and Kort (2000); Glachant and Ruester (2014)) neglecting a measure of ETE consistent with the presence of good and bad output. Other empirical analyses focus on just one policy instrument (market or environmental), missing to provide a comprehensive framework. Asane-Otoo (2016), for instance, focuses on environmental performance and its relationship with competition policy (expressed by OECD's PMR) using panel of the GHGE levels for 30 countries from 1990 to 2012. He finds a positive correlation between competition and environmental performance. Nevertheless, the main criticism comes from considering single market regulation index whereas a broader perspective should also include environmental policy instruments. Moreover, the country heterogeneity conditioning environmental performance is only modeled by the unobserved intercept of the FE model.

These puzzling outcomes seriously worry environmental policy decision makers, seeking to design the best regulatory recipes fostering environmental sustainability. Among

others, the appropriate way to mathematically model regulation-efficiency nexus is still debated and under investigation. A relevant issue emerges respect to the tendency of empirical panel studies to characterize this nexus using a one-fit-for-all relationship that potentially compromises the reliability of estimate whenever the sample is not globally representative. This study fills the gap considering both the effects of environmental and market regulations and addressing the issue of heterogeneity by means of Bayesian panel estimation techniques which tends to reduce the restrictions imposed to the estimated coefficients of the model.

3. Methodology

Our sample, since the number of observations for each cross-section is relatively small, does not allow for estimating separate models for each country; thus, a panel approach is used and the cross-section units are the EU countries. Panel data models have numerous suitable properties for estimation procedures. They provide more information than either cross-sections or time-series data, allowing more complex behavioral model specifications: panels permit the investigation of the dynamics of adjustments, which are impossible with cross-sections, while maintaining individual variations, which are lost in time series data. Finally, the use of Bayesian panels allows controlling for heterogeneity, which would otherwise leads to biased estimates. A dynamic linear model is applied to the Malmquist Index (MI) estimates obtained

by the authors in a previous research (Bigerna et al., 2019):

$$MI_{i,t} = \beta_{i1}MI_{i,t-1} + I_M(M = 1, 3, 4)\beta_{i2}PMR_{i,t} + \quad (1)$$

$$I_M(M = 2, 3)\beta_{i3}EPS_{i,t} +$$

$$I_M(M = 4)[\beta_{i4}EPS - Market_{i,t} + \beta_{i5}EPS - Non - Market_{i,t}] +$$

$$\sum_k \beta_{ik}\gamma_{ik,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

$$\epsilon_{i,t} = \mu_i + \nu_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$E(\epsilon_{i,t}) = E(\mu_i) = E(\nu_{i,t}) = 0$$

where $i = 1, \dots, 18$ states for the EU countries, $t = 2007, \dots, 2014$ for the year and $M = 1, \dots, 4$ states for the model. ϵ_{it} is the normally distributed error term including the fixed effect μ_i and the idiosyncratic error term $\nu_{i,t}$ ¹. The key explanatory variables are three OECD's indexes: PMR index, measuring the stringency of electricity market regulation and the EPS indexes, measuring the ability of regulation to put an explicit or implicit price to environmental harmful economic activities (the EPS-Market and the EPS-Non-Market, respectively). The vector $\gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ with $k = 1, \dots, 3$ is the set of control variables constituted by the output of the principal component analysis of fuelmix (Fuelmix) used in power generation, by the intensity of research and development activities (R&D) and by the combined heat and power (CHP) pen-

¹There are well-known problems in using the TFP index as a dependent variable in econometric specifications. Although this index does not suffer from boundary problems, such as other efficiency scores, its estimates are seriously affected by serial correlation. As suggested by Simar and Wilson (1999), serial correlation and bias problems are controlled implementing a bootstrap procedure in the MI computation at a previous step.

etration rate. We apply four model specifications, identified by the indicator function $I_M(\cdot)$. In the first two models, $M = 1$ and $M = 2$, we use as explanatory variable the stringency of only one type of regulation, market and environmental, respectively. In $M = 3$ we include both the PMR and the EPS indexes. In $M = 4$ we split the EPS indexes in its two sub-components.

The dynamic linear model presented may incur in endogeneity problems due to the presence of lagged dependent variable $y_{i,t-1}$ as regressor correlated with the fixed effect μ_i , thus, first difference transformation is applied to remove correlation.

Preliminary analysis is required to investigate the stationary properties and the possible cointegration of time series. If cointegration occurred, even if all the variables in first differences were stationary, the first difference regression model would be misspecified without the error-correction term. We perform two unit root tests for both the dependent variable and all the explanatory variables. We apply the Levin-Lin-Chu test (Levin et al., 2002) to verify the null hypothesis that each series share a unit root common for all panels. We always reject the null hypothesis of the presence of unit root for all series except for the market regulation variable in level. Cointegration requires the equation in level to be balanced. As pointed out by Granger (1981), if there is cointegration, it is not possible for the dependent variable, the $y_{i,t}$, to be covariance stationary and for the explanatory variable, the regulation variable, to be a random walk, because their linear combination can not be a stationary process. Therefore, the unbalanced equation already gets rid off the cointegration hypothesis. Appendix A.1 provides results of unit root tests.

Neglecting coefficients' heterogeneity in dynamic models creates correlation between

the regressors and serially correlated error terms, leading to asymptotically biased estimators. Furthermore, usual procedures such as instrumental variables techniques or first difference transformations do not work in this case. In the classical panel data literature, it is customary to pool the observations, assuming that the slope coefficients do not vary among cross sections but just allowing for cross-section specific intercept term (fixed or random). In practice it is not always the case that the data should be pooled. Pooling in the presence of parameters heterogeneity can produce misleading results. For dynamic random-coefficient models, the inconsistency of pooled panel estimators has been well established (Maddala et al., 1997) and the comparison of different estimators shows that Bayes estimators better perform in term of efficiency and sample properties (Hsiao et al., 2008). Accordingly, the problem with the two usual estimation methods of either pooling the data, or obtaining separate estimates for each cross-section is that both are based on extreme assumptions. If the data are pooled, it is assumed that slope parameters are all the same; consequently, the coefficients characterizing the regulation effects will be the same for all the countries. On the other hand, if separate estimates are obtained for each cross-section, slope parameters are all different, given the implicit, but not so reasonable, assumption that the ETE dynamics induced by regulations are completely different. The truth probably lies somewhere in between. Parameters are not exactly the same, but there is some similarity between them. One way of allowing for the similarity is to assume that all the parameters come from a joint distribution with a common mean and a nonzero covariance matrix. The authors argued that the resulting parameter estimates will be a weighted average of the overall pooled esti-

mate and the separate time series estimates based on each cross-section. Thus, each cross-section estimate is 'shrunk' toward the overall pooled estimate (i.e. 'shrinkage estimator'). According to Baltagi et al. (2004), this estimator should be preferred if the model contains lagged endogenous variables (as in our dynamic models) because it gives much more consistent parameters' values, compared to the separate cross-section estimators.

It follows we check the poolability assumption testing the null hypothesis that slope parameters are equal among cross-sections. As suggested by Baltagi (2008), instead of the standard Chow test (Chow, 1960), we perform the Roy-Zellner test that investigates the poolability of slopes in a RE model without assuming a perfect Gauss-Markov regression with homokedasticity and no serial correlation of the idiosyncratic errors. We construct RE panel linear model by stacking each cross-section regressors matrix. We then test the equality of coefficient estimates using the statistic test that, under H_0 , is a χ^2 with the degree of freedom equal to the number of restrictions. The rejection of the null hypothesis², validates the use of BSE which provides consistent and more stable predictions, compared with the pooled and the specific cross-section estimators. Moreover, given the use of the lag dependent variable as endogeneous regressor, BSE is preferred to the two-step Generalized Least Square estimator that is inconsistent for this case (Maddala et al., 2001).

²See Appendix A.2

We model the heterogeneity assumption of slope parameters as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_{ij} &= \beta_j + \nu_i & i = 1, \dots, 18; & \quad j = 1, 2, 3 \\ \beta_{ij} &\sim N(\beta_j, \sigma_{\beta_j}^2) & i = 1, \dots, 18; & \quad j = 1, 2, 3\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

where $i = 1, \dots, 18$ states for the countries and $j = 1, 2, 3$ refers to the the slope parameters referring to lagged TFP, the PMR and the EPS index, respectively. Each regression coefficient can be viewed as a random variable with a prior probability distribution having mean equal to β . Arellano-Bond estimation in Bigerna et al. (2019) are used as the prior distribution parameters for β_{ij} .

Changing in socio-economic structure and different back ground factors imply that the response parameters to regulation vary among countries. We suppose that each coefficient is the sum of two elements: the direct effect of regulatory variable on the dependent one and the indirect effect (the effect of the omitted country specific variable). The direct effects are deliberately separated from the indirect ones. The random components reflect the structural country differences (for instance, the different implementation mechanism endorsed by each country, the various transmission channels, the different incentive mechanisms for environmental sustainability) which allow the overall effect of regulation on TFP to vary among areas .

The main reason to use such approach is that, in case of misspecification, it is not correct to assume that the random noise only affects the error term. Instead it may 'infect' all the coefficients of the model. More details and technical description of the estimation procedure are reported in the Appendix B.

4. Data

The overall negative perception of traditional Pollution Haven Hypothesis stems from the nature of the usual measures of productivity growth, that does not take into account pollution as the bad output of production process. Instruments such as taxes, Emission Trading Scheme (ETS) impose additional production costs for something that would otherwise be free, inducing firms to devote resources to costly output, limit the range of production technologies available and constraint jointly the level of electricity and GHGE produced. For this reason we compute ETE through the MI, an input-output efficiency measure consistent with the concurrent presence of good and bad output, since its values increase as electricity production increases and when GHGE reduce. MI captures the TFP change between two periods using Data Envelopment Analysis. MI values greater than one signal progress in the TFP during the reference period. Values equal or lower than 1 indicate the non-variation or deterioration of TFP, respectively. We use the indirect approach (Scheel, 2001) based on transforming the values of the undesirable output through a monotone decreasing function such that the transformed data can be included as normal desirable outputs. The key explanatory variables are the PMR and the EPS indexes, sourced from the OECD database. PMR is country specific, ranges from zero to six and measures the rate of regulation in the electricity sector; given the multidimensionality of regulation, it is given by the aggregation of four components:

- Entry regulation: the presence of barriers to entry such as the presence of liberalized wholesale market for electricity, the access conditions to the electricity

transmission grid;

- Public ownership: the percentage of shares owned, either directly or indirectly, by the government in the largest firm in the electricity sector;
- Vertical integration: the degree of vertical separation between a certain segment of the electricity sector and other segments of the industry;
- Market structure: the market share of the largest company in the electricity industry.

The EPS is a country-specific measure defining the degree to which environmental policies put an explicit or implicit price on polluting or environmentally harmful behavior of the whole economy. The index ranges from zero (not stringent) to six (highest degree of stringency). As for the market regulation index, even for the EPS, the key aspect is the multidimensionality due to the multitude of instruments that can be used to design environmental policy; following the taxonomy developed by De Serres et al. (2010), the index is based on the degree of stringency of 14 environmental policy instruments primarily related to climate and air pollution (market based and not). The overall EPS index can be decomposed in two elements: the EPS-Market and EPS-Non-Market indexes. The first index refers to the effectiveness of price-based support policies such as trading scheme (i.e. ETS for CO₂, Renewable Energy Certificates), subsidy for environmentally-friendly activities (i.e. Feed-In Tariffs), taxes and charges directly applied to the pollution source or input or output of a production process (i.e. tax on emissions of NO_x or diesel tax), deposit-

refund systems (i.e. Deposit Refund Scheme for beverages). The EPS-Non-Market refers instead to quantity-based policies such as command and control regulations (i.e. emission limit value for NOx or for large size coal-fired plants) and policies supporting technology (i.e. government research and development expenditures).

We include a set of control variables constituted by the principal component of fuelmix, the intensity of research and development activities and combined heat and power penetration rate. The Fuelmix comes from the principal component analysis of the shares of sources used in each countries in the electricity generation process. Those shares were collected from the Eurostat Database. According to Canes (2012) and Pettersson et al. (2012), the Fuelmix can be thought as a proxy of both the technology changes recorded at country-level and the relative price changes of the fuels used in the generation process. The R&D comes from International Energy Agency database and it is used as an aggregated measure of all the factors proxying the unincorporated technical progress. The CHP penetration rate comes from International Energy Agency database (2010) and measures the amount of electricity produced by CHP plants which simultaneously generate electricity and useful heating and cooling from the combustion of a fuel or a solar heat collector. Since countries in our sample show different rate of penetration of this technology, we use the CHP as control variable.

Table (1) reports the set of descriptive statistics for all the variables used in the econometric analysis. Given the double dimension of panel data, statistics are computed along the two directions: the within (the cross-section) and the between (the time series) dynamics of each variables. The overall variance of each determinants has been

decomposed in the within variation (the variation over time of each cross-sections) and the between variation (the variation across country of each cross-sections). For all variables, the between variance is higher than the within variance corroborating our insight of a certain degree of heterogeneity.

[Table 1 here]

5. Results and Discussions

Table (2) reports the Bayes estimates at the aggregated level, representing the direct marginal effect of regulations. We applied four different models, considering different set of explanatory variable, starting using only the market regulation stringency index at first and then adding, step by step, the environmental policy stringency indexes. In all models regulatory coefficients are always significant on the TFP electricity sector variation, with negative sign confirming the robustness of our specification. Focusing on market regulation (Models 1, 3 and 4), the PMR coefficient is always negative, ranging from -0.031 to -0.024. It means that increasing the stringency of one point slows down the TFP change of electricity sector by 2.0% on average. EPS coefficient has the same negative impact, equal to -1.9% and -2.6% in Model 2 and 3, respectively. When we decomposed the effects of EPS in its market-based and non-market-based policy instruments (Model 4), the directions of both EPS components impacts have not changed, keeping to be negative with the EPS-Market stringency having the major decreasing effect in the change of TFP. Market-based environmental instruments reduce indeed the TFP change by 1.8% against the 1.2% of the correspondent non-market-based instruments. The negative signs of environ-

mental regulations confirm the Pollution Haven Hypothesis: tightening regulation hampers productivity because the investments in pollution controls divert resources from production.

[Table 2 here]

As the effects of regulations on the electricity sector's performance result from differences and asymmetry given the country specific response to each regulatory policy, we provide the values of Bayesian estimates representing these responses.

Figures (1) and (2) provide main statics of the posterior distributions of country specific estimates for the effect of both environmental and market regulations. These effects are those previously called the indirect effects, due to the omitted country specific variables.

[Figures 1 and 2 here]

Figure (1) reports the first, the second and the third quartile of posteriors of indirect marginal effects, each of the three points of the colored lines represents a quartile. All medians deviate from the zero vertical line, meaning that performance responses to regulations due to specific country effects significantly change the pooled direct effect. Deviations are not unidirectional even if most of the countries (those whose median lies on the right of vertical line) partially compensate the burdensome direct effects of the pooled estimates.

Figure (2) depicts the mean and variance of the distributions of these pure country ef-

fects. The distance of each point from the two lines represents the deviation from the direct marginal effect. Panels highlight the biases of country impacts from the pooled effects of regulations. Points lying on the right of the vertical line indicate countries whose performance positively respond to regulation, meaning that the country specific effect mitigates the pooled negative impacts previously estimated. Countries below the horizontal line are those whose response to regulations shows lower variability. We find significant heterogeneity of each country response to common regulatory structure, both in the levels and in the standard deviations, highlighting a non unidirectional behavior. The most scattered estimates refer to the response to the EPS-Market and these findings stress the relevance of constructing a composite index for the stringency of market-based environmental policy instruments, able to encompass the multidimensional aspects of the channels through which the policy constraints are applied. Price-based policies, such as ETS, that would seem easy to compare, actually differ in the set-up system and exemption rules as, for example, the differences in free allowance allocation provisions. The different set-ups are not encompassed in the EPS-Market index, but still they alter the incentives and influence the industry behavior at country level.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

According to 2030 Energy efficiency targets, electricity sector is facing several challenges, both technological and environmental. The causes lie on the multiple requirements associated to the dimension of the sustainability of electricity system: security, competitiveness and environment. With this study, the joint effects of the environ-

mental and market regulation have been analyzed. The main results are summarized as follows.

First, all regulatory policies (market and environmental) hinder ETE growth confirming the Pollution Haven Hypothesis; in particular, the market-based policy instruments (that impose an explicit price to environmental harmful behavior) have larger negative effect than non-market-based instruments (the quantities-based policies such as standard and limitation).

Second, a great heterogeneity exists in term of TFP growth response to regulation. Environmental OECD's indicators are effective measures that allows for cross-country comparison, shrinking the multidimensional complexity of instruments used. However, comparing electricity sectors' ETE of different countries is challenging procedure for policy makers since it requires to summarize multidimensional information, such as the fuel mix used in power generation, the location of production and investment, the market structure, all aspects that affect the extent to which countries respond to regulatory stringency. Countries with low shares of fossil fuel in electricity generation may suffer less from the enforcement of environmental policies, contrasting the impact on their TFP. Countries with pollution-intensive production located in low abatement cost regions have lower reaction to the tightening of policies and, as we showed, they compensate the overall negative effect of regulations. Moreover, at the industry level, the direction of the effect of market and environmental policies on productivity will also depend on the specific resource reallocation process: polluting firms may exit or enter the market, decrease or increase their production or outsource part of their activities. If the resulting competitive pressures will be reduced, firms'

entry-exit dynamics will slow and industry productivity will decrease.

Third, even if the stringency measures are comparable, they do not depict all aspects of the implementation systems enforced at country level. The Bayesian framework allows for capturing these composite effects of the country specific transmission channels pursued by market and environmental policies. Finally, even if some countries respond in a similar way, they show different adjustment path.

These results imply three main directions of suggestions for the policy maker. First, even if the impacts of regulations on environmental and technical performance may have the same magnitude, their variability is strongly differentiated among countries, leading to the conclusion that regulatory policies produce different scenarios in term of variability. Indeed, the volatility of the effects of regulation is a crucial determinant for the investment decision strategy in all sectors. In this context, a one size fits all policy design is inadequate. The EU 2030 Energy Efficiency targets sets the framework to spur new investments in the crucial sector of power generation, but does not take in account the country-specific differentiated responses to regulation. It follows that an appropriate policy design to target the desired amount of investment and the associated predicted profitability should be conditioned according to the specific effects of regulation on the investment decisions. In other words, the policy design should consider not only the monetary magnitude of the desired investment but also the volatility that affects the investment decision process. Second, by emphasizing the evidence that countries differently react to change in regulation, we hope to inform the political debate on the economic impact of market and environmental policies, warning on the concern to take into account the possible

divergent responses of TFP to the stringency of regulations. That is the reason why we strongly suggest the use of estimation techniques that, as the BSE, allow country marginal effects to differ, while recognizing at the same time some degree of similarity among EU electricity sectors, since these random marginal effects come from the same joint probability distribution. The BSE better forecasts the country specific possible outcomes of policy since it is able to capture with high precision the impact of policy stringency. The suggestion for the policy maker is to take into account the indirect country effect of the various transmission channels of regulation. Again, a single policy framework is not appropriate, when there are different indirect effects propagating in the economy as discussed above. Country differences in pollution intensive productions induce different reactions to policy stringency. Consequently, the same policy may be effective in one country and not in another country, because of the different economic structure and the different impact on the TFP.

Third, environmental and market regulations, at least in the EU, are characterized by combinations of instruments pertaining to European and national levels. These instruments are not isolated and their interactions influence the success of the policy mix at country level. The main concern is if these two levels are mutually supportive or undermining each other in spurring ETE. This is a crucial issue in the debate about the decentralization of environmental policies, which needs to consider the overall social welfare effects. Without entering in the debate of the relative efficacy of federal vs. local or supra-national vs. national policies in the context of the green paradox (Zhang et al., 2017), our results provide a solid suggestion to the EU policy maker. An appropriate degree of policy differentiation at the country level may

obtain higher levels of overall EU social welfare for a given level of stringency of environmental policies than would otherwise be feasible with a single common policy instrument.

Future lines of research of our study are two-fold; first, it is interesting to aim at investigating further the policy effects in terms of welfare, both at the EU and the country level, to explore the possibilities to measure compensating cross-country interventions; second, we could investigate the possible interactions among different policy instruments, market and environmental, such as taxation and stringency measures, in a general equilibrium framework, modeling explicitly the welfare impact and the efficient impact to analyze the potential trade-off between equity and efficiency of a complex policy design.

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Appendix A

A.1. Unit Root Tests

The sample size suggests the choice of the Levin-Lin-Chu (LLC) test to investigate the presence of unit roots among dependent and explanatory variables. We consider a simple panel-data model with a first-order autoregressive component, excluding a panel specific intercept or time trend:

$$\Delta y_{i,t} = \phi y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \Delta y_{i,t-1} + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (\text{A.1.1})$$

where $i = 1, \dots, 18$ indexes panels; $t = 1, \dots, T$ indexes time; y_{it} is the variable being tested.

The LLC test has the null hypothesis that each time series contains a unit root against the alternative hypothesis that each time series is stationary. The procedure works as follows:

- First, Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) regression is performed for each cross-section on the eq(A.1.1)
- Second, two auxiliary regressions are applied:
 - 1 $\Delta y_{i,t}$ on $\sum_{j=1}^p \Delta y_{i,t-1}$ to obtain residuals $\hat{\epsilon}_{i,t-1}$
 - 2 $y_{i,t-1}$ on $\sum_{j=1}^p \Delta y_{i,t-1}$ to obtain residuals $\hat{v}_{i,t-1}$
- The third step involves to run the pooled OLS regression of the standardized

residuals as follows:

$$e_{i,t} = \phi \hat{v}_{i,t-1} + \hat{\epsilon}_{i,t} \tag{A.1.2}$$

LLC tests has the null hypothesis $H_0 : \phi = 0$, that is panels i share the same autoregressive parameter ϕ different from zero. The alternative hypothesis, $H_1 : \phi < 0$, is that variable is stationary in all panels. This test is well designed for our panel data, where N is greater than T , since it is asymptotically justified when $\sqrt{N}/T \rightarrow 0$, allowing the time dimension T to grow more slowly than the cross-sectional dimension N . The test does not require error terms to have the same variance across panels.

Under the null hypothesis of unit root, $y_{i,t}$ is non-stationary and the standard OLS regression t statistic associated to the autoregressive parameter ϕ will have a non-standard distribution. Moreover, if panels contain fixed-effect, the t statistic is biased toward zero, therefore, along with the non standard t , LLC test provides the biased-adjusted t statistic asymptotically normally distributed, labeled "*Unadjusted t*".

The number of lags p used in the Augmented Dikey Fuller regression are chosen according to the Akaike Information Criterion. This process is done for each cross-section, so that different panels may use ADF regression with different number of lags. Table (A.1) shows test statistics and the p-values of tests applied to the dependent and the explanatory variables.

[Table A.1 here]

Both the unadjusted and bias-adjusted test statistics are significantly different from zero (p -value= 0.0000) for all variables except for PMR, so we reject the null hy-

pothesis of the unit-root in favor of the alternative that variables are stationary excluding PMR index. Labeled "Unadjusted t" in the output is a conventional t statistic testing common autoregressive parameter equal to zero.

A.2. Poolability Test for Coefficients Regressors

Roy-Zellner test is performed to check the equality of regressors' coefficients among panels. Table (A.2) shows results of the Roy-Zellner test implemented in Stata. The procedure is in three steps.

- First, we interact the regressors with a set of country dummies to obtain the unpooled data.
- Second, we run a random effect regression on the unpooled data.
- Finally, we test for the equality of the individual coefficients.

[Table A.2 here]

Procedure has been applied to the four model specifications and always we reject the null hypothesis of the equality of regression coefficients.

Appendix B

In a standard random-coefficient model, the Bayesian approach implies to write the basic model as follows:

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \mathbf{X}_i \beta_i + \epsilon_i \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\beta_i \sim N(\beta, \sigma_\beta^2) \quad \mathbf{i} = \mathbf{1}, \dots, \mathbf{18}; \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where \mathbf{y}_i contains MI time series, \mathbf{X}_i is the matrix of the explanatory variables, and β_i are the slopes coefficients distributed according to $N(\beta, \sigma_\beta^2)$. In the Bayesian framework, the prior distribution parameters (the mean of β_i and the variance σ_β of β_i) can be known or unknown. If they are known the posterior distribution of β_i is normal with mean and variance given by:

$$\beta_i^* = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \mathbf{X}_i' \mathbf{X}_i + \bar{\Sigma}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \mathbf{X}_i' \mathbf{y}_i + \bar{\Sigma}^{-1} \bar{\beta} \right) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\Sigma^* = \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \mathbf{X}_i' \mathbf{X}_i + \bar{\Sigma}^{-1} \right) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $\hat{\beta}_i$ are the OLS estimates of each cross-section regressions, while $\bar{\mathbf{beta}}$ and $\bar{\Sigma}$ are the prior distribution parameters for β_i .

If parameters are unknown, prior distributions for the hyperparameters need to be specified. Defined the usual non informative prior for β , Smith (1973) suggests using conjugate Wishart distribution and the independent χ^2 distributions for Σ^{-1} and

σ_i^2 , respectively, then, taking the mode of their posterior distributions as estimators:

$$\sigma_i^{2*} = \frac{1}{T + \nu_i + 2} [\nu_i \lambda_i + (\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \beta_i^*)' (\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \beta_i^*)] \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\Sigma^* = \frac{1}{N - k - 2 + \delta} \left[\mathbf{R} + \sum_{i=1}^N (\beta_i^* - \beta^*) (\beta_i^* - \beta^*)' \right] \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where k is the dimension of β and parameters ν_i , λ_i , δ and R come from the specification of the prior distributions. Approximation to vague priors are obtained setting $\nu_i = 0$, $\delta = 1$ and R to be a diagonal matrix having small positive entries. The resulting estimators take the following forms:

$$\sigma_i^{*2} = \frac{1}{T + 2} (\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \beta_i^*)' (\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbf{X}_i \beta_i^*) \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\Sigma^* = \frac{1}{N - k - 1} \left[\mathbf{R} + \sum_{i=1}^N (\beta_i^* - \beta^*) (\beta_i^* - \beta^*)' \right] \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\beta_i^* = \left(\frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}^2} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i + \Sigma^{*-1} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}^2} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i \hat{\beta}_i + \Sigma^{*-1} \beta^* \right) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$\beta^* = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i^* \quad (\text{B.10})$$

In equations (B.7)-(B.10) the prior mean β^* is an average of β_i^* , the estimate of the prior variance Σ sources from the deviations of β_i^* from their average β^* and the estimates of σ_i^2 are obtained from the residual sum of squares using β_i^* . Equations (B.7)-(B.10) should be solved iteratively with the initial iteration uses the OLS estimator $\hat{\beta}_i$ to compute β^* , Σ^* and σ_i^{*2} .

Tables and Figures

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Variables Used in the Econometric Analysis.

Variable		Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Obs.
TFP	overall	1.026	0.095	0.797	1.657	N: 144
	between		0.047	0.978	1.147	n: 18
	within		0.083	0.676	1.536	T: 8
Regulation	overall	2.239	0.811	0.871	4.434	N: 14
	between		0.705	1.016	3.445	n: 18
	within		0.430	1.480	3.764	T: 8
EPS	overall	2.777	0.543	1.400	4.133	N: 14
	between		0.440	2.075	3.592	n: 18
	within		0.333	1.811	3.623	T: 8
EPS-Market	overall	1.998	0.640	0.383	3.983	N=144
	between		0.493	1.025	2.865	n=18
	within		0.422	0.614	3.314	T=8
EPS-Non-Market	overall	3.556	0.907	1.625	5.500	N=144
	between		0.812	2.078	5.328	n=18
	within		0.442	2.477	4.727	T=8
R&D	overall	0.033	0.029	0.000	0.143	N: 14
	between		0.028	0.001	0.107	n: 18
	within		0.011	-0.010	0.070	T: 8
CHP	overall	0.166	0.136	0.000	0.786	N: 14
	between		0.125	0.030	0.462	n: 18
	within		0.059	-0.040	0.586	T: 8
Fuelmix	overall	0.020	1.179	-2.680	2.717	N: 14
	between		0.633	-1.300	1.052	n: 18
	within		1.004	-3.440	4.042	T: 8

Table 2: Bayesian Shrinkage Estimates for Different Specification of Random Coefficient Model.

M = 1^a	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	C.I.L.B^e	C.I.U.B^e
MI	-0.1976	0.0291	0.0009	-0.1981	-0.2531	-0.1403
PMR	-0.0313	0.0073	0.0002	-0.0315	-0.0451	-0.0166
R&D	-0.5713	1.2254	0.0131	-0.5611	-2.9682	1.8233
CHP	-0.0724	0.2134	0.0020	-0.0715	-0.4948	0.3474
Fuelmix	0.0081	0.0075	0.0001	0.0082	-0.0064	0.0228
U1:sigma2	0.0120	0.0105	0.0005	0.0088	0.0027	0.0416
U2:sigma2	0.0449	0.0483	0.0030	0.0288	0.0046	0.1781
sigma2	0.0156	0.0022	0.00002	0.0154	0.0118	0.0206
M = 2^b	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	C.I.L.B^e	C.I.U.B^e
MI	-0.2346	0.0339	0.0009	-0.2362	-0.2994	-0.1659
EPS	-0.0193	0.0070	0.0002	-0.0195	-0.0333	-0.0055
R&D	-0.0810	1.2524	0.0170	-0.0992	-2.5374	2.4034
CHP	-0.0626	0.2069	0.0020	-0.0623	-0.4770	0.3411
Fuelmix	0.0071	0.0074	0.0001	0.0070	-0.0075	0.0216
U1:sigma2	0.0127	0.0088	0.0003	0.0105	0.0032	0.0363
U2:sigma2	0.0464	0.0652	0.0043	0.0272	0.0042	0.2081
sigma2	0.0147	0.0021	0.0000	0.0145	0.0111	0.0195
M = 3^c	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	C.I.L.B^e	C.I.U.B^e
MI	-0.2110	0.0250	0.0009	-0.2117	-0.2592	-0.1607
PMR	-0.0244	0.0113	0.0005	-0.0248	-0.0461	-0.0019
EPS	-0.0269	0.0069	0.0003	-0.0272	-0.0402	-0.0138
R&D	-0.1136	1.2755	0.0181	-0.1143	-2.5767	2.3717
CHP	-0.0656	0.2096	0.0022	-0.0652	-0.4789	0.3522
Fuelmix	0.0073	0.0075	0.0001	0.0073	-0.0073	0.0222
U1:sigma2	0.0130	0.0089	0.0003	0.0106	0.0031	0.0365
U2:sigma2	0.0417	0.0561	0.0038	0.0244	0.0038	0.1850
U3:sigma2	0.0107	0.0088	0.0003	0.0083	0.0024	0.0334
sigma2	0.0149	0.0022	0.0003	0.0147	0.0112	0.0197
M = 4^d	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	C.I.L.B^e	C.I.U.B^e
MI	-0.1955	0.0402	0.0019	-0.1946	-0.2735	-0.1161
Overall	-0.0284	0.0125	0.0006	-0.0278	-0.0541	-0.0034
EPS-Market	-0.0182	0.0067	0.0003	-0.0182	-0.0314	-0.0051
EPS-Non-Market	-0.0127	0.0071	0.0003	-0.0127	-0.0263	0.0015
R&D	-0.2369	1.3593	0.0232	-0.2562	-2.8627	2.4975
CHP	-0.0543	0.2126	0.0024	-0.0513	-0.4791	0.3582
Fuelmix	0.0071	0.0076	0.0001	0.0072	-0.0077	0.0222
U1:sigma2	0.0109	0.0070	0.0002	0.0090	0.0030	0.0300
U2:sigma2	0.0486	0.0602	0.0038	0.0296	0.0042	0.2160
U3:sigma2	0.0110	0.0092	0.0004	0.0084	0.0027	0.0359
U4:sigma2	0.0084	0.0059	0.0003	0.0068	0.0022	0.0240
sigma2	0.0149	0.0023	0.0000	0.0147	0.0111	0.0199

a. $\Delta MI_{i,t} = \beta_{i1}\Delta MI_{i,t-1} + \beta_{i2}\Delta PMR_{i,t} + \sum_k \beta_{ik}\Delta \gamma_{ik,t}$.

b. $\Delta MI_{i,t} = \beta_{i1}\Delta MI_{i,t-1} + \beta_{i2}\Delta EPS_{i,t} + \sum_k \beta_{ik}\Delta \gamma_{ik,t}$.

c. $\Delta MI_{i,t} = \beta_{i1}\Delta MI_{i,t-1} + \beta_{i2}\Delta PMR_{i,t} + \beta_{i3}\Delta EPS_{i,t} + \sum_k \beta_{ik}\Delta \gamma_{ik,t}$.

d. $\Delta MI_{i,t} = \beta_{i1}\Delta MI_{i,t-1} + \beta_{i2}\Delta PMR_{i,t} + \beta_{i3}\Delta EPS - Market_{i,t} + \beta_{i4}\Delta EPS - Non - Market_{i,t} + \sum_k \beta_{ik}\Delta \gamma_{ik,t}$.

e. Lower and Upper bounds credible 95% credible intervals

Figure 1: Bayesian Shrinkage Estimates Statistics distribution by Country.
 25th Percentile, Median and 75th Percentile by Country.

(a) PMR

(b) EPS

(c) EPS-Market

(d) EPS-Non-Market

Figure 2: Scatter Plot of Mean and Standard Deviation of Bayesian Shrinkage Estimates by Country.

(a) PMR

(b) EPS

(c) EPS-Market

(d) EPS-Non-Market

Table A.1: Levin-Lin-Chu Unit-Root Tests.

Variable		Statistics	p value
MI_t	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-20.3577	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-18.5072	0.0000
MI_{t-1}	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-3.4910	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-3.3291	0.0004
PMR	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-0.1818	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-0.1769	0.4298
EPS	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-24.2222	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-24.0957	0.0000
EPS-Market	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-37.6833	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-38.9115	0.0000
EPS-Non-Market	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-9.7987	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-9.1578	0.0000
R&D	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-15.8113	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-15.6345	0.0000
CHP	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-7.1893	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-6.2036	0.0000
Fuelmix	<i>Unadjusted t</i>	-7.4441	0.0000
	<i>Adjusted t*</i>	-6.4752	0.0000

H_0 : Panels contain unit roots.

H_1 : Panels are stationary.

ADF regressions: 0.17 lags average (chosen by AIC).

Table A.2: Roy-Zellner Test for the Equality of Slope Parameters.

Model	Number of Restrictions	Statistic	p-value
M=1	85	108.0072	0.96
M=2	85	110.0111	0.97
M=3	102	133.4312	0.98
M=4	119	142.5617	0.98

H_0 : Slopes parameters are equal among cross sections.

We use Stata 15 to run tests; this software performs a Wald test distributed as a χ^2 with degrees of freedom equal to the number of restrictions.